

Development of Needle Punched Non-Woven Mulch Mat for Weed Suppression

D. Sheebamercy¹, S. Grace Annapoorani¹, S. M. Udaya Krithika^{2*} & K. Mani²

¹Department of Textiles and Apparel Design, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore

²Department of Fashion Technology, Sona College of Technology, Salem

Abstract:

The primary factor in the rise of sedentary human civilization is agriculture, which is the science and art of cultivating plants and livestock. Herbicides are chemicals applied to control unwanted plant species. Herbicides that target particular weed species are able to suppress them with minimal damage to the intended crop. Because natural fibers are good for reinforcing components and have convenient renewability, biodegradability, and environmental friendliness, there is increased interest in using natural fibers like Sisal, Banana, and Coir. The primary goal of the research study was to develop composites made of natural and unconventional fibers for use in agriculture. The mulch mats are composed of cotton mixed with sisal and areca nut fiber. The tomato plants were planted in pots and covered their stem with developed mulch mats and have observed for 60 days. These mulch mats are biodegradable and eco-friendly to the environment. The difference between the controlled sample and the using sample using developed mulch mat were analyzed and calculated. This technique was very helpful for the cultivation of plant growth and to avoid weed control.

Keywords: Biodegradable, eco-friendly, Mulch mats, natural fibers, non-woven

*Corresponding Author:

Dr. S. M. Udaya Krithika
Department of Fashion Technology,
Sona College of Technology,
Junction Main Road,
Salem – 636 005 TN
E-mail: udayasathyam@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Technical textiles are produced with function as the primary consideration rather than aesthetics, and they have been recognized as one of the most exciting and promising segments of the textiles industry for the future. Technical textile materials and goods are produced more for their functional and performance qualities than for their aesthetic or decorative characteristics [1]. In agriculture, textiles are used to shield crops from harsh weather. Agro textiles include knitted, nonwoven, and woven materials. The world's largest industry is agriculture. In the field of science, textiles are utilized for agricultural and animal cultivation, harvesting, storage, and protection because of modernization and significant technical breakthroughs. Textile materials are essential for gathering, storing, and safeguarding agricultural products. Agro-textiles promote a healthy farming culture by reducing the need for water, fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides. In general, textiles used in agriculture are environmentally beneficial [2].

2. Methodology

Through test methodologies, this article examines the materials, methodology, and procedures used for the development of the agro textile product known as "the mulch sheet."

2.1. Materials and Methods

2.1.1 Selection of Fibers

The first step in carrying out the project is to select the required natural fiber – Areca, Sisal and reclaimed Cotton. The fiber is selected as per literature and it is found out that Areca and Coir fiber are the most suitable fiber that can be used in the project to support plant growth effectively. Reclaimed Cotton fiber is chosen for needle punched mat [3, 4].

Figure 1: a) Reclaimed Cotton b) Areca c) Sisal

2.2 Fabric Formation

2.2.1 Blending Ratio of Natural Fiber

The fibers are weighed accurately and blended in right proportion. The selected natural fibers have been blended in different combinations as follows:

Table 1: Blending ratio of natural fibers

Fibre	Blending Ratio (As per fiber quantity)	
	Areca : cotton	50:50
Sisal: Cotton	50:50	75:25

2.2.2 Nomenclature of Sample

Table 2: Nomenclature of samples

Sr. No.	Sample code	Description
1	AC1	Areca + Cotton (50:50)
2	AC2	Areca + Cotton (75:25)
3	SC1	Sisal + Cotton (50:50)
4	SC2	Sisal + Cotton (75:25)
5	C	Coir (Commercial Mat)
6	CP	Control Plant

2.2.3 Needle Punching Technique

Lap is formed in a pilot run machine. The fibers are placed on the carding machine for cleaning and then passed over the needle punching machine to convert the fibers into lap formation. The major reasons needle punching techniques have been used are because of their excellent tearing strength and high, consistent tensile strength. Compared to other ponding techniques, needle punching technology is a low-energy, environmentally beneficial approach. The fibers are mixed and fed into the card feeder after being opened into tiny tufts in the fiber opening channel. After further opening the material from the fiber opener, a web is generated and fed into the carding machine. A thin sheet of carded web is made after the matt generated by the card feeder is opened and carded. After being shaped into a lap, the thin web sheet generated through roller carding is fed to a needle punching machine. Needle punching technology is used to produce the non-woven material and punch the lap [5, 6].

Figure 2: a) Arrangement of fibers into carding machine b) loading of fibers into carding machine c) Outcome of lap from carding machine d) Needled punching method

i. Fabrication

Mulch mat is a special kind of textile product used in agricultural fields to meet various needs. The performance of this mulch sheet is determined by taking into account the following characteristics. Measured intrinsic attributes include thickness, GSM, and width. MAG thickness gauge was used to measure the fabric's thickness in accordance with ASTM D1777 standard.

ii. Analysis

Environmental conditions

The study was carried out in the Tamil Nadu district of Coimbatore, in an agro-ecological area. The average of the weather conditions during the three months prior to the present is noted.

iii. Measurements

Measurements of the soil moisture content were carried out three, six, and nine weeks after planting, as well as during the harvesting stage, at depths of 15 and 30 cm.

iv. Growth factors of plants

The length, width, number of leaves per plant, stem length, and girth of D-leaf (strong, longest, and healthy plants) were specifically recorded. [7]

v. Testing's

For the experimental recordings, tomato plants are used because of their fast growing characteristics. Two same sized pots with identical soil types are taken. The plants' subsequent growth and quality metrics were visually monitored. Weed control, plant growth, water obtainability, and other factors were observed and measured for both mulched and unmulched potted plants. As subjective tests, these are also noted during field research. The decomposition properties of mulch mat are investigated under three different types. Three samples were buried in different types of soil, watched over every four months, and then compared. Consequently, the soil burial test yielded findings [8]

3. Results and discussion

The fibers of Areca and Sisal were straight, silky, and yellow in color. These fibers were chosen because they are strong, resilient, stretchable, and don't break down in salt water. The growth, weed control, and water retention characteristics of the non-mulched, Coir, Areca, and Sisal mulched plantations were observed; the field test yielded good results for the Sisal mulched plantation.

3.1 Visual Analysis

3.1.1 Comparative study of soil temperature and weed control measures.

Figure 3: Measure of weed control

Figure 3 shows mulch in pot leaving only the seeded area barley for photosynthesis of plant seedlings.

3.2 FTIR analysis of fibers

The primary components of Areca, including cellulose, hemicelluloses, and lignin, correspond to specific bands in the FTIR wavelength peaks collected between 4000 cm^{-1} and 500 cm^{-1} . The peak values between 3334.92 and 2941.44 cm^{-1} were attributed to the stretching of hydrogen bonds, or OH, on the surface of cellulose. The presence of cellulose and shemicelluloses is shown by the next peak value of 2129.41 cm^{-1} , which displays the CH stretching of the alkyl group. The acetyl and uronic groups' ester of the hemicelluloses or the ester linkage of carboxylic groups of the ferulic and p-coumeric acids of the lignin or hemicelluloses are linked to the prominent peak of the Areca at 1734.01 cm^{-1} . The cellulose chain's -C - O - C bond is the cause of the band at 1462.04 cm^{-1} .

Sisal's FTIR spectra was recorded between 4000 and 500 cm^{-1} . It is noted that the intensities of the peak corresponding to the -OH stretching vibrations in the 3352.28 cm^{-1} area are higher due to the esterification of the

hydroxyl groups through benzylation. The -CH stretching vibration peak at 2941.44 cm⁻¹ indicates the existence of cellulose and hemicelluloses [5]. The presence of lignin and the C = O stretching of the carboxyl group are indicated by the peak value of 1735.93 cm⁻¹. The hydroxyl group of cellulose exhibits typical axial vibration, which gives rise to a peak at 1620.21 cm⁻¹. The related hydrogen group is responsible for the peak at around 1058.92 cm⁻¹. The wave numbers are 777.31cm⁻¹, as shown by the presence of aromatic rings. [9, 10]

Figure 4: FTIR of Areca and Sisal fiber.

3.3 XRD analysis of fiber

Powder XRD for equatorial reflections, performed at a scanning rate of one degree per minute, produced two notable peaks in the diffractogram at 20.0 and 18.0 (figure 5), indicating the semi-crystalline character of the Areca and Sisal fiber. The peak values are represented by the relative intensities $I_{20} = 1272$, $I_{20} = 1032$, and $I_{18} = 760$, $I_{18} = 900$, the crystalline index and percentage crystallinity have been determined as follows:

$$C.I. = (I_{20} - I_{18}) / I_{20}$$

The crystalline and amorphous intensities at 2θ scale at 20o and 18o, respectively, are denoted by I_{20} and I_{18} . Therefore, the crystalline index for the Areca and Sisal inflorescence fiber is 0.40, 0.12.

Figure 5: XRD pattern of Areca and Sisal fiber.

3.4 Fabric weight (GSM)

Table 3: Fabric weight (GSM)

Sr. No.	Fabric	AC1(50:50)	AC2(75:25)	SC1(50:50)	SC2(75:25)
1.	Non-woven	677	790	1303	1869
2.		696	753	1200	1900
3.		654	802	1189	1760
4.		690	781	1400	1800
5.		632	788	1580	1560
Mean value		669.8 gms	782.8 gms	1334 gms	1778 gms

From Table 3, it is observed that Fabric Weight of the sample AC1, AC2, SC1, and SC2 samples showed variations. The Fabric Weight was statistically analyzed using T-Test and observed that AC1 with the value 669.8gms, AC2 with the value 782.8gms, SC1 with the value 1334gms and SC2 with the value 1778gms. SC2 value was found to be higher than the other samples. [11]

3.5 Thickness of the Non-woven

Table 4: Thickness of the non-woven

Sr. No.	Fabric	AC1(50:50)	AC2(75:25)	SC1(50:50)	SC2(75:25)
1.	Non-woven	6.29	3.44	6.62	4.02
2.		5.92	5.24	6.09	4.39
3.		6.19	5.55	7.19	4.69
4.		6.85	5.82	6.44	5.29
5.		5.25	6.21	6.10	5.79
Mean Value		6.1mm	5.25mm	6.49 mm	4.48 mm

From Table 4, it is observed that Thickness of the sample AC1, AC2, SC1, and SC2 samples showed variations. The Fabric thickness was statistically analyzed using T-Test and observed that AC1 with the value 6.1mm, AC2 with the value 5.25mm, SC1 with the value 6.49mm and SC2 with the value 4.48mm. SC1 value was found to be higher than the AC1. [12]

3.6 Air Permeability of Non-Woven

Table 5: Air Permeability of the non-woven

Sr. No.	Fabric	AC1(50:50)	AC2(75:25)	SC1(50:50)	SC2(75:25)
1.	Non-woven	17.75	19.72	27.6	51.28
2.		15.77	17.75	27.6	49.30
3.		19.75	19.72	25.64	47.33
4.		13.70	17.75	23.66	45.36
5.		19.72	15.77	21.69	47.33
Mean Value		17.33 cm³/s/cm²	18.14cm³/s/cm²	25.24 cm³/s/cm²	28.12 cm³/s/cm²

From Table 5, it is observed that Air permeability of the sample AC1, AC2, SC1, and SC2 samples showed variations. The air permeability of fabric was statistically analyzed using T-Test and observed that AC1 with the value 17.33 cm³/s/cm², AC2 with the value 18.14 cm³/s/cm², SC1 with the value 25.24 cm³/s/cm² and SC2 with the value 28.12 cm³/s/cm². SC2 value was found to be higher than other fibers and the least is AC1.

3.7 Porosity of Non-woven

Table 6: Porosity of Non-woven

Sr. No.	Fabric	AC1(50:50)	AC2(75:25)	SC1(50:50)	SC2(75:25)
1.	Non-woven	0.94	0.97	0.97	0.97
2.		0.96	0.99	0.99	0.97
3.		0.97	0.97	0.98	0.99
4.		0.94	0.98	0.97	0.96
5.		0.96	0.97	0.98	0.98
Mean Value		0.95g/cm³	0.97g/cm³	0.97g/cm³	0.97g/cm³

Table 6 and figure 6, it is observed that Porosity of the sample AC1, AC2, SC1, and SC2 samples showed variations. The Porosity of fabric was statistically analyzed using T-Test and observed that AC1 with the value 0.95 g/cm³, AC2 with the value 0.97 g/cm³, SC1 with the value 0.97 g/cm³ and SC2 with the value 0.97 g/cm³. AC2, SC1, and SC2 values were found to be equal and AC1 shows slight variation.

3.8 Soil burial test

Field method

Table 7: Soil burial test of non-woven in field

Sr. No.	No. of Days	Weight of the sample before testing (gms)				Weight of the sample after testing (gms)			
		50:50		75:25		50:50		75:25	
		AC1	SC1	AC2	SC2	AC1	SC1	AC2	SC2
1.	70	0.630	0.860	0.680	0.650	0.610	0.850	0.660	0.630

Figure 6 Images of Soil burial Test

From the above Table 7, in that field method showed weight changes in a sample when compared with laboratory method. It is observed that there were weight changes with AC1 showed a value of 0.630gm before testing and 0.610gm after testing whereas AC2 showed a value of 0.680gm before testing and 0.660gm after testing. Whereas SC1 showed the value of 0.860gm before testing and 0.850gm after testing. Like that SC2 showed the value of 0.650gm of before testing and 0.630gm of after testing. [13]

3.9. Weeds growth tabulation

Table 8: Weeds growth

Sr. No.	Weeks	AC1 (50:50)	AC2 (75:25)	SC1 (50:50)	SC2 (75:25)	C	CP
1.	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2.	2	0	0	0	0	0	6
3.	3	0	0	0	0	1	14
4.	4	0	0	0	0	4	17
5.	5	1	1	1	1	5	23

From the Table 9 shows a weed suppression. It is observed that there was no growth of weeds for four continuous weeks for all the developed non-woven mulch mat covered pots, whereas there was weed growth of 6 nos in 2nd week, 14 nos in 3rd week, 17 nos in 4th week and 23 nos in 5th week. And finally, in the last week, it is observed that there were 1 no of weed growth in AC1 & AC2 and SC1 & SC2, whereas in control plant the growth was 23. This proved that there was great weed suppression. [14]

3.10 Wicking test

Table 9: Wicking test

Sr. No.	Fabric	AC1(50:50)	AC2(75:25)	SC1(50:50)	SC2(75:25)
1.	Non-woven	1.6mm	1mm	3.8mm	5.4mm

From the above Table 9, the findings of the wicking of the needle punched fabrics are shown. SC2 has a superior wicking of 5.4 mm which was followed by sample SC1 of 3.8 mm wicking. AC1 & AC2 has lower wicking of 1.6 & 1 when compared to all the samples SC1 showed good wicking.

3.11 Sinking test

Figure 10: Sinking test

S. No.	Fabric	AC1(50:50)	AC2(75:25)	SC1(50:50)	SC2(75:25)
1.	Non-woven	50 min	45 min	20 min	14 min

From the above Table 10, represents the results of the sinking test of needle-punched samples. Sample AC1 takes the maximum time of 50 mins to sink were as AC2 of 45 mins and SC1 of 20 mins and SC2 of 14 mins respectively. Thus the sample SC2 showed good results.

4. Conclusion

This study has shown the prevention of weed control and helps to grow a tomato plant easily in potted plants. The mulch mat made from Areca, Sisal, and Cotton was developed using a needle punching machine with two different ratios. Two fibers are evaluated in FTIR and XRD analysis. Mats are evaluated in various testing like GSM, non-woven thickness, air permeability, soil burial test, porosity of non-woven, density of non-woven. The application process of mulch mat be simple and effective. This property on agriculture increases plant growth. Areca and Sisal fiber are abundantly available in India as well other countries. Atlast, the developed non-woven needle-punched is eco-friendly & bio-degradable. From the research work it is found that Sisal fiber SC2 is found to be the best fiber weed suppression. [15]

References:

- [1] Grace Annapoorani, S.: *Agro Textiles and its application*, ISBN- 9789385059360, Wood Head Publishing India Pvt Ltd, (2018)
- [2] Bhavani,K,;Ningdalli Mallikarujun,; Sunilkumar, N.M.: Agro textiles – Their applications in agriculture and scope for utilizing natural fibers in agrotech sector, *International Journal of Applied Home Science*, Vol.4 (2017) No (7 & 8), pp. 653-662, ISSN – 2394 1413
- [3] Subrahmaniyan Kasirajan et al. Polyethylene and biodegradable mulches for agricultural applications: a review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 2012, 32, p.501-529
- [4] Mohankumar, G.C.2008. A study of short areca fibre reinforced Phenol formaldehyde composites. *Proceedings of the World Congress on Engineering*, 2: 978-988
- [5] Rajan A, Kurup JG, Abraham TE. Biosoftening of arecanut fiber for value added products. *Biochemical Engineering Journal*, 2005, 25(3):237-42
- [6] Srinivasa CV, Arifulla A, Goutham N, Santhosh T, Jaeethendra HJ, Ravikumar RB, Anil SG, Kumar DS, Ashish J. Static bending and impact behaviour of areca fibers composites. *Materials & Design*, 2011, 32(4):2469-75
- [7] Areca, Publication of Central Plantation Crops Research Institute, Kasargod, India, 2007
- [8] Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research, Volume 36,p 2Paulo. R.L.Lima,;Rogerio.J.Santos,; Saulo.R.Ferreiro.; Romildo.D. Toledo Filho,; Characterization and treatment of sisal fiber residues for cement-based composite application. *Engineering Agriculture*, Vol .34 (2014), No (5), pp. 234-238
- [9] Sreekumar .P.A,; RedouanSaiab,; Jean Marc Saites,; Nathalie Leblanc,; Kuruvilla Joseph,; Unnikrishnan.G,; Sabu Thomas,; Thermal behavior of chemically treated and untreated sisal fiber-reinforced composites fabricated by resin transfer molding. *Composite Interfaces*, Vol. 15 (2008), No (6), pp. 629 – 633
- [10] Kasirajan and Mathieu, “Polyethylene and Biodegradable mulches for agricultural application: A Review”, *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, April 2012
- [11] “Mulches and Mulching for erosion control”, Technical notes U.S department of agriculture natural resources conservation service plant materials-8, Spokane, Washington, February 2005
- [12] “Mulch mats a novel way for trees to outgrow weeds”, *Science Spin*, Issued 27
- [13] *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, Volume-2, Issue-4, April 2019, B.Jeyanthi, S.Geetharani, J.R.Krishnaindhu, “Development of Needle Punched Mulch Mat using Natural Fibers”
- [14] Kasirajan and Mathieu, “Polyethylene and biodegradable mulches for agricultural application: A Review”, *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, April 2012
- [15] “Mulch mats a novel way for trees to outgrow weeds”, *Science Spin*, Issue 27